

The Shabti of the Viceroy of Kush Hori I (UB-014)

Object Biography and Provenance Study

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Persistent Identifiers

Object UB-014

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Abstract

UB-014 is a small-format faience ushabti of Viceroy Hori I. This Deep Publication follows an object-biographical approach, combining epigraphic, archaeological, and provenance-historical observations. Particular emphasis is placed on distinguishing between the documented modern provenance and the transmitted, as yet independently unverified origin from the tomb of Hori at Tell Basta. At the same time, the study demonstrates that parts of the Hori I group had entered circulation prior to the 1944 excavation, and that an early dispersal phase – hitherto only inadequately documented – must therefore be assumed.

Catalogue Entry

Object: Ushabti of the Viceroy of Kush Hori I

Material: Faience (white-glazed)

Dimensions: Height 10.8 cm; Width 3.1 cm

Dating: Late Dynasty XX, reign of Ramesses III to Ramesses IV (after de Haan 2019), ca. 1170–1140 BCE

Provenance:

Probably from the tomb of Hori I at Tell Basta (Bubastis), reportedly recovered ca. 1944; the present study suggests, however, that parts of the group had entered circulation prior to this date;

Collection of Elizabeth Khayat, New York;

Sotheby Parke-Bernet, New York, 13 December 1979, lot 85;

Collection of the W. Benson Harer Family Trust;

acquired from the US art market through the German art market (Galerie Alte Römer, Cologne), 2023; present collection (since 2026).

Location: Private collection

Inventory number: UB-014

Description: Mummiform ushabti of white-glazed faience with dark brown to violet-brown painted details. The figure wears a tripartite wig and a usekh collar. The hands are crossed over the chest holding agricultural implements; a seed bag is indicated on the back. A vertical hieroglyphic inscription column is present on the front face.

Inscription: The Osiris designation (*wsjr*) is clearly legible in the upper section; the inscription belongs unambiguously to the known formula group of the ushabtis of the Viceroy of Kush Hori I. Due to wear and the state of preservation, a fully sign-accurate reading of all individual signs is not possible in every detail. The reconstructed reading is based on published parallels (Habachi 1957; Gauthier 1928; de Haan 2019).

Transliteration (reconstructed from series parallels): *wsjr ḥrj s3-nswt n k3š*

Extended formula variant: *sdḥ wsjr s3-nswt n k3š sš ḥrj*

Translation: "The Osiris Hori, King's Son of Kush."

Extended variant: "The Illuminated One, the Osiris, the King's Son of Kush, the Scribe Hori."

Published: Scott, G. D.: *Temple, Tomb and Dwelling: Egyptian Antiquities from the Harer Family Trust Collection*. Exhibition catalogue, University Art Gallery, California State University, San Bernardino, 8 January – 8 March 1992, San Bernardino 1992, p. 201, no. 150 (with illustration p. 203, there erroneously captioned as no. 151; cf. de Haan 2019, no. 8, who already questions the erroneous height measurement of 12.5 cm).

Remarks: The object belongs to a clearly definable group of approximately thirty known faience ushabtis of Hori I.

Typologically it corresponds closely to the examples published by Habachi (1957), Gauthier (1928), and de Haan (2019).

Note on publication: The illustration of this object in Scott (1992) is incorrectly published on p. 203 under no. 151, while the correct catalogue entry no. 150 is assigned on p. 201.

Historical and Biographical Context: Hori I., Viceroy of Kush

[Section 3 — Historical and Biographical Context: Hori I., Viceroy of Kush]

Shabti UB-014 is part of a closed tomb inventory commissioned for his burial at Tell Basta by one of the most prominent Ramesside administrators of the late 20th Dynasty: Hori I., "King's Son of Kush" (sꜣ-nsw n Kꜣö), viceroy over Wawat and Kush. A scientifically defensible interpretation of the object presupposes that the person of the deceased and his historical milieu are at least sketched in their secure outlines. The present section consolidates the current state of research on Hori I.'s person, family, term of office and sphere of activity. It thereby provides the argumentative backdrop for the subsequent chapters on the object biography (Section 4), the provenance assessment (Section 5), the typology and workshop context (Section 6) and the dispersal history (Section 7).

The presentation follows the prosopographical state of research, in particular the specialised study by Niek de Haan (2019), which systematically catalogues the known Hori shabti corpus¹. Where findings are uncertain or contested between scholarly positions, this is made explicit.

[Subsection 3.1 — Person, Family and Origins]

Father and son are prosopographically secure: Hori I. is the son of one Kama (also Kamaw), and his son Hori II. becomes his successor in the viceregal office. The filiation is documented through the statue Cairo JE 36665 and anchored in G. A. Reisner's standard prosopography². Hori I.'s wife bears the name Khayt and holds the title "Singer of Mehyt" (ömeyt n Mhyt). Mehyt is the lion-headed consort of Onuris/Anhur and was worshipped at This (Thinis, 8th Upper Egyptian nome). This implies for the Hori family a supra-regional network ranging from Bubastis to Middle Egypt — a remarkable finding for a Ramesside elite family from the eastern Nile Delta. Shabtis of Khayt herself are attested and provide additional typological anchor points for the family. A second son is attested as Webekh-sen (Wbḥw-sn) — tentatively read by Reisner (1920) as "Wentawuat?", left unnamed by Gauthier (1928). Habachi (1981, pp. 61 f.) clarifies the reading on the basis of Hori I.'s Sehel inscription (no. 37) and additionally identifies Webekh-sen as the maker of a lintel from his father's residential house at Buhen³. An iconographic affinity between individual Hori shabtis and pieces of a Horemheb was observed by de Haan (2019), but it cannot at present be condensed into a secured genealogical statement⁴.

Striking is the family's firm attachment to Bubastis (Tell Basta) in the eastern Nile Delta. Both Hori I. and Hori II. were buried there and not in Thebes or Nubia — a pattern unusual for a viceroy of Kush. Most office-holders in this position came from Theban or Memphite official families and were accordingly buried in the Theban rock-cut necropoleis or at Nubian residential sites. That the Hori family remained permanently anchored at an eastern Delta site fits politically into the phase in which Bubastis was gaining importance; the city later became the residence and namesake of the 22nd (Libyan) Dynasty. The neighbouring tomb of the vizier Iuty at Tell Basta (tomb no. 1130, analysed by Auenmüller 2021) confirms that the eastern Delta sustained a substantial elite-burial tradition within Ramesside high state service⁵.

[Subsection 3.2 — Career and Tenure]

Hori I. came to the viceregal office from a military career. Attested intermediate titles are "First Charioteer of His

¹de Haan, Niek: The shabtis of the King's Son of Kush Hori. 2019.

https://www.academia.edu/39314315/The_shabtis_of_the_Kings_Son_of_Kush_Hori

²Reisner, George A.: The Viceroys of Ethiopia (II). In: *Journal of Egyptian Archaeology* 6/1 (1920), pp. 73–88.

<https://www.jstor.org/journal/jegyarch>

Ägyptisches Museum Kairo, Statue of Hori, Son of Kama. Filiation source for Hori I. Cited after Reisner 1920. (museum object)

³Habachi, Labib: Sixteen Studies on Lower Nubia. Supplement aux Annales du Service des Antiquités de l'Égypte, Cahier 23. Le Caire, IFAO 1981. Late synthetic collection of the viceroy studies; contains Chap. III (Graffiti and Work of the Viceroys of Kush in the Region of Aswan, originally Kush V, 1957) and Chap. IX (Viceroys of Kush during the New Kingdom, first publication).

local:images/deep/Habachi_1981_Sixteen_Studies_on_Lower_Nubia_CASAE23.pdf

⁴de Haan, Niek: The shabtis of the King's Son of Kush Hori. 2019.

https://www.academia.edu/39314315/The_shabtis_of_the_Kings_Son_of_Kush_Hori

⁵Auenmüller, Johannes: The Ramesside Vizier Iuty from Bubastis. In: *Ägypten und Levante / Egypt and the Levant XXXI* (2021), pp. 15–43.

local:/Users/dirk/Uschabti_Collection_Beckers/Hori/Auenmueller-2021-Vizier-Iuty.pdf

Majesty” (kdn tpj n hm.f) and ”King’s Messenger to Every Foreign Land” (wpwtj-nsw r h3swt nbt). This trajectory fits the unstable political situation at the transition from the 19th to the 20th Dynasty: Siptah, Tausret and Sethnacht needed loyal military officers in the strategically important south of Egypt. Hori I.’s predecessor in the viceregal office was probably a Hori-predecessor Seti, whose activity is plausibly placed under Merenptah or Amenmesse; the transition is not seamlessly documented in the sources. Habachi (1981, p. 166) provides a precise sequence for the early career: in year 3 of Siptah, Hori is sent to Nubia as ”First Charioteer” and ”King’s Messenger”; in year 6 he is promoted to viceroy and retains the office through the reigns of Tausret and Sethnacht ⁶.

A secure date anchor for Hori I.’s early tenure is provided by a rock graffito from Elephantine dated to year 6 of Siptah (conventionally ca. 1191 BCE). Another Elephantine graffito is assigned to year 6 of Ramesses III (ca. 1178 BCE). Both attestations frame an activity span covering several decades and are extensively discussed in the older research literature ⁷. Niek de Haan (2019) places the career of Hori I. — and thus the Hori-I. shabti corpus — in the reigns of Ramesses III and Ramesses IV, and thereby chronologically in the late phase of a tenure that outlasted several pharaonic transitions. The present Deep Publication follows de Haan’s dating and places Hori I.’s burial and thus the production of shabti UB-014 in the late phase of Ramesses III to Ramesses IV — i.e. in a period of approximately 1170–1140 BCE ⁸.

This dating is not undisputed. In the older literature, and in part also in online information from museum collections — for example the Institute of Egyptian Art and Archaeology of the University of Memphis — Hori I. is occasionally still placed under Seti II, which by current research is too early ⁹. A recently submitted preprint hypothesis (Whelan et al., December 2025) draws attention to a tension in the conventional chronology of the viceroys — the combined tenures of viceroys Hori I., Setau, Kama and Hori II. arithmetically yield an unusually long total span — and proposes for that a parallelism of the 19th and 20th Dynasties for discussion ¹⁰. This position has so far not been academically accepted and is not adopted here; however, that an open discussion point (”dynastic glitch”) exists in the chronological framework of the late Ramesside period remains noted as a research desideratum.

[Subsection 3.3 — Titulary]

The principal office bore the title ”King’s Son of Kush” (s3-nsw n K3ö). In addition the following titles are epigraphically attested for Hori I.:

- ”First Charioteer of His Majesty” (kdn tpj n hm.f) — military career title
- ”King’s Messenger to Every Foreign Land” (wpwtj-nsw r h3swt nbt) — diplomatic function
- ”Overseer of the Gold Lands of Amun-Re” (jnj-r3 h3swt nbw n Jmn-Rc) — control of the Nubian gold mines
- ”Royal Scribe” (sö-nsw) — administrative sphere

The inscription of shabti UB-014 takes up — in its reconstructed full form — the combination ”Osiris, King’s Son of Kush, Scribe Hori” (wsjr hrj s3-nswt n k3ö sö hrj) and thereby links the principal office title with the scribe title. The

⁶Habachi, Labib: Sixteen Studies on Lower Nubia. Supplement aux Annales du Service des Antiquites de l’Egypte, Cahier 23. Le Caire, IFAO 1981. Late synthetic collection of the viceroy studies; contains Chap. III (Graffiti and Work of the Viceroys of Kush in the Region of Aswan, originally Kush V, 1957) and Chap. IX (Viceroys of Kush during the New Kingdom, first publication). [local: images/deep/Habachi_1981_Sixteen_Studies_on_Lower_Nubia_CASAE23.pdf](https://www.jstor.org/journal/jegyarch)

⁷Reisner, George A.: The Viceroys of Ethiopia (II). In: Journal of Egyptian Archaeology 6/1 (1920), pp. 73–88. <https://www.jstor.org/journal/jegyarch>

Whelan, Paul: Mere Scraps of Rough Wood? 17th–18th Dynasty Stick Shabtis in the Petrie Museum and other collections. London 2007. <https://www.goldenhouse.uk/>

⁸de Haan, Niek: The shabtis of the King’s Son of Kush Hori. 2019. https://www.academia.edu/39314315/The_shabtis_of_the_Kings_Son_of_Kush_Hori

⁹Institute of Egyptian Art and Archaeology, University of Memphis, Shabti of Hori, Viceroy of Kush (Inv. 1989.3.3). Online publication; legacy Sety II dating, considered too early in current research. <https://www.memphis.edu/egypt/exhibit/hori.php>

¹⁰Whelan, Paul et al.: The History of the Hori(s) is not ’a Hoary Old Tale’. Preprint, December 2025. Not peer-reviewed; cited here only as ongoing methodological discussion regarding a possible chronological ”glitch” in the late Ramesside viceroy succession. <https://figshare.com/>

military and diplomatic career titles remain — as is customary on faience shabtis of this scale — unconsidered. This finding is typical of the reduced title forms used in the funerary context.

[Subsection 3.4 — Source Evidence]

Despite the political importance of the viceregal office, Hori I. is thinly documented in monumental sources. The key attestations outside the large shabti corpus can be reduced to a few pieces:

- Elephantine graffiti (in situ): date anchor year 6 Siptah; a further graffito is assigned to year 6 Ramesses III, but the attribution is not undisputed ¹¹.
- Statue Cairo JE 36665 (Egyptian Museum Cairo): bears the filiation formula "Hori, son of Kama" and is securely attributable to Hori I. ¹².
- Family tomb at Tell Basta (excavated 1944 by Habachi): provides the burial context for Hori I. and probably also for Hori II. The publication is Habachi's monographic supplement to the *Annales du Service des Antiquités de l'Égypte* ¹³.
- Doorframe stela British Museum EA66668 (London): bears a Ramesses IV titulary and a viceroy "Hori". The attribution to Hori I. or Hori II. is debated in the literature; the mainstream line attributes the piece to Hori II. ¹⁴.
- Statue Copenhagen Glyptothek AEIN 49: a Merenptah-period comparative piece, predominantly attributed in research not to Hori I. but to the predecessor Seti or to a homonymous person.
- Sehel graffito no. 37 (Habachi 1981): in situ on Sehel Island, with an invocation of Bastet of Bubastis; names Hori I. together with his son Webekh-sen. In the older literature (Reisner 1920) still attributed to Hori II., re-assigned by Habachi 1981 to Hori I. on the basis of the Bubastis-Bastet invocation and the titulary ¹⁵.
- Lintel from Hori I.'s residential house at Buhen: made by his son Webekh-sen, cited after Habachi 1981 ¹⁶.
- Two viceroy statues from Bubastis: first published by Naville (1891, pp. 42, 44, 45, pls. 36 N; 38 E); attributed in scholarship either to Hori I. or to Hori II., with no unambiguous differentiation possible ¹⁷.

Several generalisations carried along in popular accounts do not withstand source criticism. Concrete rock inscriptions, stelae or graffiti from Aniba (administrative seat of Wawat) are, for Hori I. — unlike for his predecessors Messui and

¹¹Whelan, Paul: *Mere Scraps of Rough Wood? 17th–18th Dynasty Stick Shabtis in the Petrie Museum and other collections*. London 2007.

<https://www.goldenhouse.uk/>

¹²Ägyptisches Museum Kairo, Statue of Hori, Son of Kama. Filiation source for Hori I. Cited after Reisner 1920. (museum object)

Reisner, George A.: *The Viceroys of Ethiopia (II)*. In: *Journal of Egyptian Archaeology* 6/1 (1920), pp. 73–88. <https://www.jstor.org/journal/jegyparch>

¹³Tell Basta. Cairo 1957.

<https://www.meretsegerbooks.com/pages/books/M0743b/habachi-labib/tell-basta>

¹⁴British Museum London, doorframe stela of viceroy Hori with Ramesses IV titulary. Attribution to Hori I or Hori II discussed in the literature; mainstream attribution to Hori II.

https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/Y_EA66668

¹⁵Habachi, Labib: *Sixteen Studies on Lower Nubia*. Supplement aux *Annales du Service des Antiquités de l'Égypte*, Cahier 23. Le Caire, IFAO 1981. Late synthetic collection of the viceroy studies; contains Chap. III (Graffiti and Work of the Viceroys of Kush in the Region of Aswan, originally Kush V, 1957) and Chap. IX (Viceroys of Kush during the New Kingdom, first publication). `local:images/deep/Habachi_1981_Sixteen_Studies_on_Lower_Nubia_CASAE23.pdf`

¹⁶Habachi, Labib: *Sixteen Studies on Lower Nubia*. Supplement aux *Annales du Service des Antiquités de l'Égypte*, Cahier 23. Le Caire, IFAO 1981. Late synthetic collection of the viceroy studies; contains Chap. III (Graffiti and Work of the Viceroys of Kush in the Region of Aswan, originally Kush V, 1957) and Chap. IX (Viceroys of Kush during the New Kingdom, first publication). `local:images/deep/Habachi_1981_Sixteen_Studies_on_Lower_Nubia_CASAE23.pdf`

¹⁷Naville, Edouard: *Bubastis (1887-1889)*. Egypt Exploration Fund, Memoir 8. London 1891. First systematic publication of the Bubastis complex; documents inter alia two viceroy statues found at Bubastis (pp. 42, 44, 45, pls. 36 N; 38 E).

<https://archive.org/details/bubastis08navi>

Tell Basta. Cairo 1957.

<https://www.meretsegerbooks.com/pages/books/M0743b/habachi-labib/tell-basta>

for the late viceroy Panehesy — not documented in freely accessible publications. An Aswan inscription, however, is secured with the Sehel graffito no. 37 (Habachi 1981). Inscriptions held in the viceregal office from Buhen are primarily documented for Hori II.; for Hori I., the lintel from his Buhen residential house, made by his son Webekh-sen, constitutes an archaeological attestation¹⁸. Concrete military operations or revolts in Nubia during his tenure are likewise not transmitted. The relationship to Bay, the “kingmaker” at Siptah’s court, cannot be reconstructed from the available sources. The exact date of death also remains open.

[Subsection 3.5 — Bubastis and the Family Tomb]

The tomb of Hori at Tell Basta was officially excavated in 1944 by Labib Habachi and published in the ASAE supplement *Tell Basta* (1957)¹⁹. Architecturally, Habachi described — the description refers primarily to the Hori-II. complex but presumably to the entire installation — a corridor of fired bricks with three vaulted chambers on each side; walls and floors were executed in fired bricks (with the clear function of moisture protection in the Delta), upper wall sections and roofs by contrast in mud bricks. The findings had already been plundered in antiquity. The exact stratigraphy of the family complex — whether Hori I. and Hori II. shared a single common installation or two separate tombs — is not unambiguously graspable in the published form; a systematic re-evaluation of Habachi’s diaries and plans remains a research desideratum.

Hori I.’s attachment to Bubastis manifests itself not only in the choice of burial site but also directly in epigraphic evidence. In the Sehel graffito no. 37 — a small inscription recorded in the Aswan region — Hori I. invokes not the local Cataract deities (Khnum, Satis, Anukis) but the Eastern Delta goddess Bastet: “Bastet, mistress of Bubastis, mistress of heaven and consort of the gods. Made for the viceroy of Kush, the overseer of the Southern Lands, the royal scribe Hori, the blessed. His beloved son, the first charioteer of His Majesty, Webekh-sen”²⁰. Habachi comments: “Hori I seems to have been very loyal to his home deity” (1981, p. 62). That a viceroy in the Aswan region invokes not the local deities but a Delta goddess is an exceptionally explicit epigraphic witness to the Bubastite identity of the family and independently supports the archaeologically documented choice of burial site.

Of significance for the later dispersal history is Habachi’s own report on illegal tomb-robbing activity at Tell Basta that had already set in before his excavation. This note is quoted and analysed in detail in the provenance assessment (Section 5) (cf. there; Habachi 1957, p. 6; cf. Auenmüller 2021, p. 28). The parallel plundering history of the neighbouring tomb of vizier Iuty, whose grave goods had already surfaced on the Cairo market before 1926 (Auenmüller 2021, pp. 27–28), supports the picture of an early dispersed find complex and provides the immediate comparative horizon for the Hori-I. shabti scattering²¹.

[Subsection 3.6 — State of Research on Hori I and his Shabti Corpus]

The standard prosopography of the Ramesside viceroys is still Reisner (1920)²². It is substantially expanded and corrected in points of detail by Habachi’s late synthesis in the *Sixteen Studies on Lower Nubia* (1981) — in particular through the identification of Sehel inscription no. 37 as a witness to Hori I., the reading of the son’s name as Webekh-sen, and the precise career sequence under Siptah, Tausret and Sethnacht²³. The fundamental excavation publication

¹⁸Habachi, Labib: *Sixteen Studies on Lower Nubia*. Supplement aux Annales du Service des Antiquites de l’Egypte, Cahier 23. Le Caire, IFAO 1981. Late synthetic collection of the viceroy studies; contains Chap. III (Graffiti and Work of the Viceroys of Kush in the Region of Aswan, originally Kush V, 1957) and Chap. IX (Viceroys of Kush during the New Kingdom, first publication).
local:images/deep/Habachi_1981_Sixteen_Studies_on_Lower_Nubia_CASAE23.pdf

¹⁹Tell Basta. Cairo 1957.
<https://www.meretsgerbooks.com/pages/books/M0743b/habachi-labib/tell-basta>

²⁰Habachi, Labib: *Sixteen Studies on Lower Nubia*. Supplement aux Annales du Service des Antiquites de l’Egypte, Cahier 23. Le Caire, IFAO 1981. Late synthetic collection of the viceroy studies; contains Chap. III (Graffiti and Work of the Viceroys of Kush in the Region of Aswan, originally Kush V, 1957) and Chap. IX (Viceroys of Kush during the New Kingdom, first publication).
local:images/deep/Habachi_1981_Sixteen_Studies_on_Lower_Nubia_CASAE23.pdf

²¹Auenmüller, Johannes: The Ramesside Vizier Iuty from Bubastis. In: *Ägypten und Levante / Egypt and the Levant XXXI* (2021), pp. 15–43.

local:/Users/dirk/Uschabti_Collection_Beckers/Hori/Auenmueller-2021-Vizier-Iuty.pdf

²²Reisner, George A.: The Viceroys of Ethiopia (II). In: *Journal of Egyptian Archaeology* 6/1 (1920), pp. 73–88.
<https://www.jstor.org/journal/jegyparh>

²³Habachi, Labib: *Sixteen Studies on Lower Nubia*. Supplement aux Annales du Service des Antiquites de l’Egypte, Cahier 23. Le Caire, IFAO 1981. Late synthetic collection of the viceroy studies; contains Chap. III (Graffiti and Work of the Viceroys of Kush

for the burial context is Habachi (1957)²⁴; for the first publication of the Bubastis complex, in which two viceroy statues with Hori attribution are documented as well, Naville (1891) must be cited²⁵. For shabti typology, the relevant standard works are to be consulted: Schneider (1977), Aubert/Aubert (1974), Stewart (1995) and — for methodological questions on the stick-shabti corpus of earlier periods — Whelan (2007)²⁶. The central specialised study on the Hori shabti corpus is Niek de Haan, *The shabtis of the King's Son of Kush Hori* (2019), which typologically and collection-historically catalogues some thirty known specimens and remains the authoritative reference for the present publication²⁷. For embedding the Hori complex within the Ramesside elite-burial activity at Tell Basta, Auenmüller (2021) provides the immediate comparative horizon via the Iuty tomb²⁸.

Current methodological discussions — such as the Whelan preprint of December 2025 on the parallelism of the 19th and 20th Dynasties — are registered but deliberately not adopted in the argumentation of the present contribution²⁹. Among the living specialists with whom contact exists or existed for UB-014, in particular Niek de Haan (ushabtis.com) and Dik van Bommel (ushabtis.com) should be mentioned. Van Bommel's clarification of 8 April 2026 on the identification of Superior Galleries Lot 55 as the Bab-el-Gasus priest Hori (21st Dynasty) — and thus not as the viceroy Hori I. — has definitively revised the older attribution going back to W. Benson Harer and is treated in detail in the provenance assessment (Section 5)³⁰.

An open research discussion concerns the numbering of the Hori viceroys. In the *Sixteen Studies* (1981, p. 152), Habachi proposes that the viceroy designated here as Hori I. (son of Kama, in office under Siptah–Sethnacht) be counted as "Hori II." and his son as "Hori III.", on the grounds that an even earlier, very briefly serving viceroy "Hori" is attested with the usual determinative in a Yuny inscription, although no inscriptions of his own have come down to us. The standard literature published after Habachi 1981 (de Haan 2019, Auenmüller 2021; Aubert 1974 and Schneider 1977 having preceded Habachi's reassignment proposal) has not adopted this re-numbering and continues to use the count "Hori I. (father) — Hori II. (son)". The present publication follows the consensus standard numbering; Habachi's argument is registered here as an alternative scholarly position.

From this source and research situation the framework emerges within which the object-biographical and provenance-historical investigation of UB-014 will be unfolded in the following chapters: a Ramesside viceroy who is astonishingly thinly documented in sources yet prosopographically clearly outlined, with a firm tie to Bubastis, an anciently plundered family tomb and a shabti corpus of some thirty known specimens that was serially dispersed in the 20th century.

in the Region of Aswan, originally Kush V, 1957) and Chap. IX (Viceroys of Kush during the New Kingdom, first publication).
local: [images/deep/Habachi_1981_Sixteen_Studies_on_Lower_Nubia_CASAE23.pdf](https://www.meretssegerbooks.com/pages/books/M0743b/habachi-labib/tell-basta)

²⁴Tell Basta. Cairo 1957.

<https://www.meretssegerbooks.com/pages/books/M0743b/habachi-labib/tell-basta>

²⁵Naville, Edouard: *Bubastis* (1887-1889). Egypt Exploration Fund, Memoir 8. London 1891. First systematic publication of the Bubastis complex; documents inter alia two viceroy statues found at Bubastis (pp. 42, 44, 45, pls. 36 N; 38 E).

<https://archive.org/details/bubastis08navi>

²⁶Shabtis, Vol. II. Leiden 1977.

<https://search.worldcat.org/title/604438597>

Statuettes égyptiennes. Paris 1974.

<https://data.bnf.fr/fr/documents-by-rdt/11889387/te/page1>

Stewart, Harry M.: *Egyptian Shabtis*. Shire Egyptology, Princes Risborough 1995.

<https://search.worldcat.org/title/33105043>

Whelan, Paul: *Mere Scraps of Rough Wood? 17th–18th Dynasty Stick Shabtis in the Petrie Museum and other collections*. London 2007.

<https://www.goldenhouse.uk/>

²⁷de Haan, Niek: *The shabtis of the King's Son of Kush Hori*. 2019.

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²⁸Auenmüller, Johannes: *The Ramesside Vizier Iuty from Bubastis*. In: *Ägypten und Levante / Egypt and the Levant XXXI* (2021), pp. 15–43.

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²⁹Whelan, Paul et al.: *The History of the Hori(s) is not 'a Hoary Old Tale'*. Preprint, December 2025. Not peer-reviewed; cited here only as ongoing methodological discussion regarding a possible chronological "glitch" in the late Ramesside viceroy succession.
<https://figshare.com/>

³⁰Van Bommel, Dik (ushabtis.com): Personal communication, 7–8 April 2026. Identification of Superior Galleries lot 55 as Bab el-Gasus priest Hori (Dyn. XXI), not viceroy Hori I.

<https://www.ushabtis.com>

Object Biography

Ushabti UB-014 belongs to a small, well-defined group of approximately thirty known figures attributed to the "King's Son of Kush" Hori I, a high administrative official of the late Ramesside period under Ramesses III and Ramesses IV. The title "King's Son" is to be understood here as an official title referring to the viceroyalty over Nubia.

The original manufacture of the object is therefore to be placed in the late 12th century BCE. Typologically and epigraphically, the piece belongs to the group of small-format, mostly light to white-glazed faience ushabtis of this period, produced in series for high-ranking officials.

The transmitted provenance gives the tomb of Hori at Tell Basta (ancient Bubastis in the eastern Nile Delta) as the original depositional context. The archaeological investigations of this necropolis were published primarily by Labib Habachi³¹. However, a direct, archaeologically documented find context for the present piece cannot be independently verified. The attribution to the tomb of Hori is therefore currently to be assessed as a transmitted, but not primary-documentation-supported statement.

According to the transmitted object history, the ushabti is said to have been recovered "presumably around 1944" from the tomb. This statement falls chronologically in the period before or parallel to systematic excavations and could indicate an unregulated recovery or looting, as documented for many sites in the Nile Delta during this period³². Independent confirmation of this date is not currently available; the statement is therefore to be treated as a traditional, unverified transmission.

By the mid-20th century at the latest, the object was in the possession of the antiquities dealer Elizabeth Khayat, whose family was active in the international antiquities trade. No confirmed information is currently available regarding the precise circumstances of acquisition within this network, though an origin from the Egyptian art market of the first half of the 20th century is probable.

The first documented public market record for the present ushabti is provided by the auction at Sotheby Parke-Bernet on 13 December 1979 (New York, Sale 4324, lot 85). Elizabeth and Marie Khayat (New York) jointly consigned on this occasion a group of four faience ushabtis of Hori I (lots 82–85), of which three are illustrated in the auction catalogue³³. The handwritten annotations in the catalogue attribute the academic title "Dr." to Elizabeth. Marie Khayat (1913–1991) was Elizabeth's sister and likewise belonged to the family of the antiquities dealer Azeez Khayat. Beyond the Hori group, the Khayat sisters consigned additional objects: a Ptolemaic/early Roman limestone stele (lot 80) and a separate alabaster ushabti of Dynasty XIX/XX (lot 81). This indicates the dispersal of a more extensive family holding. Lot 82 contains the only complete inscription reading in the catalogue ("the Osiris, the Inspector, the King's Son of Kush, the Royal Scribe Hori") with a reference to Aubert, nos. 43–47. The present object (lot 85) is recorded with a height of 10.8 cm and an estimate of \$600–900. The identification of UB-014 with lot 85 therefore rests on this catalogue description and the typological and metric correspondence with the illustrated parallels, not on a direct pictorial comparison. With this auction entry, the object is for the first time unambiguously documentable in a publicly recorded context.

The ushabti subsequently entered the collection of W. Benson Harer, where it remained for several decades. The Harer collection is known for its specialisation in ancient Egyptian minor arts, underscoring the object's placement within a curated private collection.

A further documented phase in the modern object biography is its inclusion in the exhibition "Temple, Tomb and Dwelling: Egyptian Antiquities from the Harer Family Trust Collection" (1992)³⁴. The figure was displayed from 8

³¹Tell Basta. Cairo 1957.

<https://www.meretsegerbooks.com/pages/books/M0743b/habachi-labib/tell-basta>

³²Sebakhin note.

<https://www.ucl.ac.uk/museums-static/digitalegypt/archaeology/sebakhin.html>

³³Sotheby Parke-Bernet, New York, Sale 4324, 13 December 1979. Elizabeth and Marie Khayat, consignors. Lots 80–85.

local: images/deep/Sothebys_1979_Sale4324_Lots80-85.pdf

³⁴Temple, Tomb and Dwelling. 1992.

<https://archive.org/details/templetombdwelli0000scot>

January 1992 to 8 March 1992 at the University Art Gallery, California State University, in cooperation with the San Bernardino County Museum. Illustrated and described in the accompanying catalogue: Gerry D. Scott, *Temple, Tomb, and Dwelling: Egyptian Antiquities from the Harer Family Trust Collection (1992)*, p. 201, no. 150 (with illustration p. 203, there erroneously captioned as no. 151). (see Fig. 1) (see Fig. 2)

The inclusion of the present ushabti in this exhibition context is significant in that it documents its placement within an academically curated framework. Unlike purely commercial presentations in the art trade, such an exhibition is subject to scholarly selection criteria, curatorial review, and institutional responsibility.

In 2023, the object moved from the US art market into the German art market. It entered the present collection in early 2026. This marks the continuation of the object's modern collecting history, now under conditions of systematic scholarly documentation, digital recording, and comparative analysis within the known Hori group.

In summary, the object biography can be described as a sequence of manufacture, presumed deposition in the tomb at Tell Basta, presumably uncontrolled recovery in the 20th century, subsequent circulation in the international art market, and finally integration into a scholarly-oriented private collection. While the modern provenance from 1979 onward is well documented, and the most recent stages – German art market 2023, present collection since 2026 – are fully recorded, the earlier section of the object's history – particularly the precise find context – remains a central field of ongoing research.

Provenance Assessment

[Provenance Research: The Khayat Network]

The attribution of the present ushabti to the group of faience ushabtis of the Viceroy of Kush Hori I from Tell Basta can be regarded as established on the basis of iconographic, metric, and epigraphic correspondences.

Labib Habachi documented a total of 15 ushabtis during the excavation of the tomb of Hori I in 1944, including 9 faience examples with a height of approximately 11 cm ³⁵.

By contrast, Niek de Haan ³⁶ documents a total of approximately 30 known ushabtis of this series in museum and private collections. This discrepancy can only be explained by the fact that a significant portion of the original series had already been removed from the tomb prior to the official excavation.

Additional independent market and collection references support this interpretation. One example from the Rijksmuseum van Oudheden in Leiden (inv. F 1970/1.1) demonstrably entered the collection via the art market, probably through the Dutch dealer Moger around 1970. Equally, the present ushabti is documented in the US art market from 1979 at Sotheby Parke-Bernet, consigned by Dr. Elizabeth Khayat. (see Fig. 3) The piece subsequently appears in the Harer Family Trust collection. These parallel lines demonstrate that parts of the series were in circulation long before Habachi's scholarly documentation.

A decisive terminus ante quem is provided by the publication of Henri Gauthier ³⁷, in which a faience ushabti from the tomb of Hori II is illustrated, almost identical in material, size, execution, and inscription to the ushabtis of the Hori I group. This publication demonstrates that corresponding pieces were already accessible outside a secured excavation context by 1928 at the latest. (see Fig. 4)

It therefore follows necessarily that parts of the ushabti series from the tomb of Hori I had entered circulation before 1944. The most probable mechanism is undocumented local excavation activity in the vicinity of Tell Basta in the early 20th century, well documented for the Nile Delta (sebakhin activity ³⁸ and informal digging). This form of gradual, often agriculturally motivated disturbance of archaeological contexts represents one of the central factors in the early dispersal history of such object groups.

A vivid testimony to the scale of these activities is provided by Labib Habachi himself, who reports on Tell Basta: "[T]he place has always been subject to illicit digging which has often resulted in the discovery of important objects, very few of which were handed to the Department of Antiquities. The majority instead found their way to dealers. [...] Even in the railway station dealers were always present to meet the passengers and show them objects coming mostly from Tell Basta" (Habachi 1957, p. 6; cited after Auenmueller 2021, p. 28) ³⁹. This testimony illustrates how directly grave goods from the elite tombs at Tell Basta — including the tombs of the viceroys Hori I and Hori II and of the vizier Iuty (tomb no. 1130) — entered the art trade. The parallel looting history of the adjacent tomb of Iuty, whose funerary equipment appeared on the Cairo market before 1926 (Auenmueller 2021, pp. 27–28), supports the assumption of a comparable early dispersal pattern for the Hori I ushabtis.

Direct involvement by Habachi in the removal or trade of finds is not documented and cannot be established on the basis of the current source material.

³⁵Tell Basta. Cairo 1957.

<https://www.meretsgerbooks.com/pages/books/M0743b/habachi-labib/tell-basta>

³⁶de Haan, Niek: The shabtis of the King's Son of Kush Hori. 2019.

https://www.academia.edu/39314315/The_shabtis_of_the_Kings_Son_of_Kush_Hori

³⁷Le tombeau de Hori. ASAE 28 (1928), pp. 133–138.

<images/deep/Gauthier-1928-133.pdf>

³⁸Sebakhin note.

<https://www.ucl.ac.uk/museums-static/digitalegypt/archaeology/sebakhin.html>

³⁹Tell Basta. Cairo 1957.

<https://www.meretsgerbooks.com/pages/books/M0743b/habachi-labib/tell-basta>

Auenmüller, Johannes: The Ramesside Vizier Iuty from Bubastis. In: *Ägypten und Levante / Egypt and the Levant XXXI* (2021), pp. 15–43.

local:/Users/dirk/Uschabti_Collection_Beckers/Hori/Auenmueller-2021-Vizier-Iuty.pdf

The comprehensive reconstruction of the Khayat network is supplemented by a significant primary source: the complete estate file of Azeez Khayat from the Surrogate's Court, County of New York (File P-2451/1945, 1946–1947)⁴⁰. This 233-page court record, obtained in April 2026 from the NYC Surrogate's Court Record Room, documents for the first time with legal precision the composition and distribution of Azeez Khayat's New York antiquities inventory.

The file reveals the legal foundations for the transfer of the paternal collection to the seven children, including Elizabeth and Marie Khayat. Under oath, the parties described the New York holdings as "hundreds of antiquities", "Egyptian antiques and antique jewelry", and "ancient art objects". Explicitly named are "Egyptian bronze figures", "glass objects", "necklaces", and "antique jewelry" — an object category combination fully consistent with a dealer stock that included Egyptian burial objects such as ushabtis⁴¹.

Crucial is the proof of continuous custody since 1933: Victor A. Khayat testified under oath that the antiquities had been stored "ever since 1933" in Room 405, 366 Fifth Avenue, NYC, following Azeez's return to Palestine — a 14-year documented custody until distribution. The appraisal by the New York State Department of Taxation & Finance (Harold A. Forstenzer, Estate Tax Bureau, September–October 1945) resulted in a total value of approximately \$76,385: \$64,815 for office contents plus \$11,570.09 for jewelry in a bank safe deposit box⁴².

The distribution occurred in March 1947 "in kind" — that is, the objects were physically divided among the seven children, not auctioned or liquidated. Elizabeth Khayat Bouton and Marie Khayat, as two of the seven heirs, received their portions in kind and retained them privately for 32 years (1947–1979) before consigning the Hori I ushabtis to Sotheby's⁴³.

A key to the modern provenance of UB-014 lies in the reconstruction of the Khayat network. The transmitted information regarding Elizabeth Khayat gains its full significance only when placed not in isolation but within the family, estate, and trade contexts of the Khayat family.

Research into the family of Azeez Khayat shows it to be a Levantine family with substantiated connections to the international trade in Egyptian antiquities. Azeez or Aziz Habib Khayat appears as a long-standing antiquities dealer and collector who had publicly traded in Egyptian, Greek, and Roman antiquities in New York from at least the 1910s onwards. Auction catalogues are documented for 1912, 1919, 1924, 1925, and 1926; particularly important is the Anderson catalogue of 1924, which explicitly names "Egyptian Ushabtiu" and links the offered pieces to Azeez Khayat's own collecting and procurement travels in Egypt, Palestine, Syria, and Greece. This establishes for the provenance research of UB-014 that the Khayat holdings included not only Egyptian antiquities in general but also

⁴⁰Surrogate's Court, County of New York. Estate of Azeez Khayat, File P-2451/1945. Complete probate file (233 pages, 16 documents), 1946–1947. Obtained 27 April 2026 from Kim Sulik, Archivist/Records Manager, NYC Surrogate's Court Record Room. Search fee \$90 USD, Receipt #399226. Documents the composition, appraisal (~\$76,385), and distribution "in kind" of Azeez Khayat's NYC antiquities inventory ("hundreds of antiquities," "Egyptian antiques and antique jewelry") among his seven children in March 1947, including Elizabeth Khayat Bouton and Marie Khayat as future Sotheby's consignors (1979).

local:Khayat_NYC_Surrogate_Court_Probate.pdf

⁴¹Surrogate's Court, County of New York. Estate of Azeez Khayat, File P-2451/1945. Complete probate file (233 pages, 16 documents), 1946–1947. Obtained 27 April 2026 from Kim Sulik, Archivist/Records Manager, NYC Surrogate's Court Record Room. Search fee \$90 USD, Receipt #399226. Documents the composition, appraisal (~\$76,385), and distribution "in kind" of Azeez Khayat's NYC antiquities inventory ("hundreds of antiquities," "Egyptian antiques and antique jewelry") among his seven children in March 1947, including Elizabeth Khayat Bouton and Marie Khayat as future Sotheby's consignors (1979).

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⁴²Surrogate's Court, County of New York. Estate of Azeez Khayat, File P-2451/1945. Complete probate file (233 pages, 16 documents), 1946–1947. Obtained 27 April 2026 from Kim Sulik, Archivist/Records Manager, NYC Surrogate's Court Record Room. Search fee \$90 USD, Receipt #399226. Documents the composition, appraisal (~\$76,385), and distribution "in kind" of Azeez Khayat's NYC antiquities inventory ("hundreds of antiquities," "Egyptian antiques and antique jewelry") among his seven children in March 1947, including Elizabeth Khayat Bouton and Marie Khayat as future Sotheby's consignors (1979).

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⁴³Surrogate's Court, County of New York. Estate of Azeez Khayat, File P-2451/1945. Complete probate file (233 pages, 16 documents), 1946–1947. Obtained 27 April 2026 from Kim Sulik, Archivist/Records Manager, NYC Surrogate's Court Record Room. Search fee \$90 USD, Receipt #399226. Documents the composition, appraisal (~\$76,385), and distribution "in kind" of Azeez Khayat's NYC antiquities inventory ("hundreds of antiquities," "Egyptian antiques and antique jewelry") among his seven children in March 1947, including Elizabeth Khayat Bouton and Marie Khayat as future Sotheby's consignors (1979).

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ushabtis specifically. ⁴⁴

The genealogical structure of the family can be traced with surprising precision in parts. A museum record with the dedication "Given in memory of Azeez Khayat by his daughters, the Misses Marie and Susette Khayat" firmly establishes that Marie and Susette were daughters of Azeez Khayat. ⁴⁵

A probate notice dated 1943 for Azeez Habib Khayat of Haifa further places Susette Khayat and Elizabeth Khayat together in the estate context. This establishes Elizabeth not merely as a namesake of the other Khayats, but as directly embedded in a legally relevant connection surrounding Azeez's death and estate. ⁴⁶

The membership of Elizabeth Khayat in the family of Azeez Khayat is additionally supported by primary source evidence from the Thirteenth Census of the United States (1910): Elizabeth Khayat is recorded in the household of Azeez Khayat in New York (U.S. Census Collection, 1910). ⁴⁷ (see Fig. 5)

An additional genealogical dataset (Ancestry) lists Elizabeth Khayat (1909–2005), Mary Khayat (1913–1991), and Susette "Susie" Khayat (1898–1980) as children of Azeez/Aziz Khayat. This secondary source corresponds closely in all three cases with the independently documented life dates and estate connections of the three women, and is confirmed by the 1910 census entry for Elizabeth. ⁴⁸

Of particular significance is how the family holdings moved after Azeez's death. The Khayat line continued in the New York trade, documented under the names "Azeez Khayat Gallery" and later "Ancient Arts Gallery," 505 Fifth Avenue, New York; the gallery is closely associated with Susette Khayat. ⁴⁹

The Sotheby's context of 1979, in which "Elizabeth and Marie Khayat, New York" appear together as consignors (Sale 4324, lots 80–85), and the 1980 documented connection of "Elizabeth and Marie Khayat" with the "Estate of Susette Khayat," demonstrate that the three women represent a closely linked estate and dispersal line. The handwritten annotations in the catalogue attribute the academic title "Dr." to Elizabeth, suggesting an educated and possibly academically engaged heir. This fits the picture of a deliberate estate administration rather than a distress sale. The five jointly consigned objects (lots 80–85) comprise, in addition to the four Hori ushabtis, a Ptolemaic/early Roman limestone stele and a separate alabaster ushabti of Dynasty XIX/XX. This demonstrates the breadth and quality of the Khayat family holdings. ⁵⁰ While lots 82–84 are illustrated in the auction catalogue, lot 85 – the present object UB-014 – is only described as "similar to the preceding" and not illustrated. The identification of UB-014 with lot

⁴⁴Catalogue of Rare Ancient Egyptian, Greek and Roman Glass ... Collection of Mr. Azeez Khayat. New York 1912.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Catalogue_of_Rare_Ancient_Egyptian_Greek.html?id=XjMKOQEACAAJ
Ancient Works of Art Collected by Azeez Khayat of New York. New York, 31 January–1 February 1919.
<https://www.clevelandart.org/print/art/1919.10>

A Notable Collection of Ancient Egyptian, Greek, Roman and Persian Antiquities. New York, 12–13 March 1924.
<images/deep/khayat-catalog-1924-page-20.jpg>

Rare & Beautiful Egyptian, Greek, Roman & Persian Antiquities. New York, 6–7 March 1925.
https://archivesspace.csusb.edu/repositories/3/archival_objects/10768

Rare & Beautiful Egyptian, Greek, Roman, Phoenician & Persian Antiques. New York, 26–27 March 1926.
https://archivesspace.csusb.edu/repositories/3/top_containers/524

⁴⁵Memorial inscription for Azeez Khayat.
<https://chrysler.emuseum.com/objects/18998/head-of-satyr>

⁴⁶Probate notice for Azeez Habib Khayat.
<https://www.jpress.org.il/>

⁴⁷Thirteenth Census of the United States, 1910. New York, New York County: Azeez Khayat household; Elizabeth Khayat listed as household member. Sammlung US-Volkszählung 1910, via Ancestry.com (accessed 2026).
images/deep/Census_1910_Khayat_household.jpg

⁴⁸Genealogical dataset (project screenshot); Elizabeth Khayat (1909–2005), Mary Khayat (1913–1991), Susette "Susie" Khayat (1898–1980) listed as children of Azeez/Aziz Khayat. Confirmed for Elizabeth by KHAYAT_CENSUS_1910.
<images/deep/ancestry-khayat.jpg>

⁴⁹Smithsonian Archives of American Art.
<https://www.aaa.si.edu/collections/doll--richards-gallery-records-9315/historical-note>

George B. Gordon records.
<https://www.penn.museum/collections/archives/findingaid/552748>

⁵⁰Sotheby Parke-Bernet, New York, Sale 4324, 13 December 1979. Elizabeth and Marie Khayat, consignors. Lots 80-85.
local:images/deep/Sothebys_1979_Sale4324_Lots80-85.pdf

Missing source: KHAYAT_SOTHEBY_1980

85 therefore rests on this catalogue description and the typological and metric correspondence with the parallels. Indications regarding the subsequent whereabouts of the pieces are provided by de Haan (2019), who shows that examples from this group reappear in the art market in 1982.

Given the demonstrated trading activity of Azeez Khayat with ushabtis (Anderson Galleries 1924), his direct connection to Egyptian excavation contexts, and the fact that Elizabeth Khayat consigned in 1979 a closed group of four typologically identical Hori I ushabtis together with her sister Marie, an acquisition of these objects as part of the family inheritance is to be assumed with considerably higher probability than an independent collection purchase. The consignment of such a closed group argues structurally against successive individual purchase and suggests that the objects were transmitted as part of a coherent family holding – probably in the course of the inheritance process documented by the 1943 probate notice.⁵¹ An object-specific primary record for Azeez Khayat's ownership is, however, not available; the interpretation remains a source-critically graduated, but well-founded research hypothesis supported by the convergence of several independent indicators.

An additional, hitherto unconsidered reference arises from the Azeez Khayat auction catalogue (Anderson Galleries, 1924). The ushabti published there under no. 167 exhibits a typological proximity to the Hori I group. This demonstrates that ushabtis of the same morphological spectrum were already in the possession of Azeez Khayat in 1924.

A structural finding from the estate file supports the thesis of a longer-term family collection: Evelyn K. Paulson warned the court that Victor could "make substitutions for numerous of these antiquities" because "said items might look identical to the unskilled eye"⁵². This warning demonstrates both the family's awareness of the objects' value and the difficulty of authentication — relevant context for the collection's integrity. The fact that Elizabeth Khayat Bouton, as a medical doctor (Ph.D.), professor at New York Medical College, and former US Army Medical Corps officer (1944–1946), was an educated professional capable of deliberate, informed estate management — not a casual seller — underscores the plausibility of the long-term, conscious retention of the Hori ushabtis until 1979⁵³.

A lead that proved erroneous in the course of provenance research concerns the auction catalogue of Superior Galleries (Los Angeles / Beverly Hills, December 1978). According to the statement of Dr. W. Benson Harer (transmitted by Bryan Kraemer, RAFFMA; email correspondence of 13 February 2026⁵⁴), the ushabti was said to have been published as lot 55 in this catalogue. A systematic verification by the ushabti specialist Dik van Bommel (ushabtis.com) established, however, that lot 55 does not refer to the viceroy Hori I but to a homonymous priest Hori from the Bab el-Gasus cache (Dynasty XXI)⁵⁵. The catalogue itself is documented in the archival holdings of the Pfau Library Special Collections (CSUSB) as part of the W. Benson Harer Auction Catalog Collection (SC-015)⁵⁶. The Superior Galleries auction is thus excluded as a provenance station for UB-014; the first documented public market record

⁵¹Probate notice for Azeez Habib Khayat.

<https://www.jpress.org.il/>

Sotheby Parke-Bernet, New York, Sale 4324, 13 December 1979. Elizabeth and Marie Khayat, consignors. Lots 80-85.

local:images/deep/Sothebys_1979_Sale4324_Lots80-85.pdf

⁵²Surrogate's Court, County of New York. Estate of Azeez Khayat, File P-2451/1945. Complete probate file (233 pages, 16 documents), 1946–1947. Obtained 27 April 2026 from Kim Sulik, Archivist/Records Manager, NYC Surrogate's Court Record Room. Search fee \$90 USD, Receipt #399226. Documents the composition, appraisal (~\$76,385), and distribution "in kind" of Azeez Khayat's NYC antiquities inventory ("hundreds of antiquities," "Egyptian antiques and antique jewelry") among his seven children in March 1947, including Elizabeth Khayat Bouton and Marie Khayat as future Sotheby's consignors (1979).

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⁵³Surrogate's Court, County of New York. Estate of Azeez Khayat, File P-2451/1945. Complete probate file (233 pages, 16 documents), 1946–1947. Obtained 27 April 2026 from Kim Sulik, Archivist/Records Manager, NYC Surrogate's Court Record Room. Search fee \$90 USD, Receipt #399226. Documents the composition, appraisal (~\$76,385), and distribution "in kind" of Azeez Khayat's NYC antiquities inventory ("hundreds of antiquities," "Egyptian antiques and antique jewelry") among his seven children in March 1947, including Elizabeth Khayat Bouton and Marie Khayat as future Sotheby's consignors (1979).

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⁵⁴Bryan Kraemer (RAFFMA), email correspondence with the author, 13 February 2026.

personal communication

⁵⁵Van Bommel, Dik (ushabtis.com): Personal communication, 7–8 April 2026. Identification of Superior Galleries lot 55 as Bab el-Gasus priest Hori (Dyn. XXI), not viceroy Hori I.

<https://www.ushabtis.com>

⁵⁶W. Benson Harer Auction Catalog Collection (SC-015).

https://archivesspace.csusb.edu/repositories/3/archival_objects/8016

remains the Sotheby Parke-Bernet auction of 13 December 1979.

In summary, UB-014 is not to be understood as an isolated object but as part of a multigenerational dispersal history mediated via the art trade, closely connected to the Khayat network.

Typology and Workshop Context

The faience ushabtis of the Viceroy of Kush Hori I form a clearly definable and unusually homogeneous group within late Ramesside ushabti production. Characteristic features are the material (white-glazed faience), the small size of approximately 10.5–11.5 cm, the dark brown to violet-brown interior drawing, a single-line frontal inscription, and standardised iconographic elements such as tripartite wig, usekh collar, crossed implements, and seed bags.

A particularly close typological parallel exists with the ushabtis from the tomb of Hori II (son of Hori) published by Gauthier (1928, pl. 16–17) ⁵⁷. These exhibit almost identical characteristics with respect to material, proportion, colouring, and inscription structure. The correspondences go beyond general stylistic similarities and concern specific execution details of the painting as well as the arrangement of the hieroglyphs.

A further comparative piece from this group is held in the Rijksmuseum van Oudheden Leiden (inv. F 1970/1.1), published in Schneider (1977, Ld. 3.3.0.5) and illustrated in de Haan (2019, fig. 6) ⁵⁸. This example confirms the typological coherence of the group outside the original burial context.

Of particular significance is a comparison from the art market not hitherto systematically considered: the Azeez Khayat auction catalogue (Anderson Galleries, New York, 1924) includes under no. 167 a ushabti (ill. p. 11; description p. 20) ⁵⁹ showing a close morphological correspondence to the Hori ushabtis.

This correspondence concerns particularly: - the slender, slightly tapering body form, - the proportions of head and torso, - the single vertical inscription on the front face, - and the characteristic dark interior drawing on light faience ground.

This combination is not generic within Egyptian ushabti production but is typical of a closely defined workshop tradition, most probably to be localised in the eastern Nile Delta.

(see Fig. 6) (see Fig. 7) (see Fig. 8)

The catalogue's dating ("18th Dynasty") is to be assessed critically and probably reflects commercial simplification rather than a well-founded typological classification. The formal criteria argue clearly for an attribution to the late Dynasty XX or the Third Intermediate Period.

A comparable imprecision in dynasty attribution is also found in the publication of the University of Memphis example (inv. 1989.3.3) ⁶⁰, which is assigned there to Dynasty XIX. The formal criteria in this case equally argue unambiguously for an attribution to the late Dynasty XX, as supported by the published parallels in Habachi (1957) and de Haan (2019). Such dating imprecisions are characteristic for objects of this group and reflect the difficulties of precisely classifying Ramesside serial productions without a secured excavation context.

Taken together with the published pieces from the tomb of Hori I (Habachi 1957) ⁶¹, the comparative examples in Gauthier (1928), and the Leiden piece, a consistent picture emerges of a regionally bound workshop production encompassing at least two high-ranking officials – Hori I and Hori II.

⁵⁷Le tombeau de Hori. ASAE 28 (1928), pp. 133–138.
[images/deep/Gauthier-1928-133.pdf](#)

⁵⁸Shabtis, Vol. II. Leiden 1977.

<https://search.worldcat.org/title/604438597>

de Haan, Niek: The shabtis of the King's Son of Kush Hori. 2019.

https://www.academia.edu/39314315/The_shabtis_of_the_Kings_Son_of_Kush_Hori

⁵⁹A Notable Collection of Ancient Egyptian, Greek, Roman and Persian Antiquities. New York, 12–13 March 1924.

[images/deep/khayat-catalog-1924-page-20.jpg](#)

Plate showing ushabtis (no. 167).

[images/deep/khayat-catalog-1924-page-11.jpg](#)

Description page for no. 167.

[images/deep/khayat-catalog-1924-page-20.jpg](#)

⁶⁰Missing source: MEMPHIS_HORI

⁶¹Tell Basta. Cairo 1957.

<https://www.meretsegerbooks.com/pages/books/M0743b/habachi-labib/tell-basta>

The Khayat piece extends this comparative group with a clearly art-market-documented example already in 1924. This confirms not only the stylistic coherence of the workshop production but also demonstrates that corresponding ushabti types were already in circulation well before the 1944 excavation.

Distribution and Dispersal

The archaeological basis is provided by Labib Habachi's excavation in 1944, in which a total of 15 ushabtis were documented in the tomb of Hori I, including nine faience examples⁶². This inventory does not, however, represent the original total number.

Niek de Haan's compilation (2019) documents approximately 30 known ushabtis of the Hori group in museum and private collections⁶³. The difference between the documented excavation inventory and the current total establishes that a significant portion of the series must have been removed from the tomb prior to the official excavation.

The distribution of these objects today can be divided into several independent dispersal lines that together present a consistent picture of the fragmentation of the original series:

- Excavation context (Cairo): The pieces documented by Habachi and transferred to the Egyptian Museum constitute the archaeologically secured core inventory and represent the only unambiguously context-bound group.
- Dutch market line (Leiden / Moger): The example inv. F 1970/1.1 in the Rijksmuseum van Oudheden Leiden entered the collection probably via the art market, likely through the Dutch dealer Moger around 1970⁶⁴. This documents an independent dispersal line outside the Cairo inventory.
- American market line (Khayat / Harer): Further examples, including the present ushabti, are documented in the US art market from 1979 onwards (Sotheby Parke-Bernet, consigned by Dr. Elizabeth Khayat)⁶⁵ and were subsequently published in the Harer Family Trust collection⁶⁶.
- Academic collection (Memphis): A further example is held in the collection of the Institute of Egyptian Art and Archaeology, University of Memphis (inv. 1989.3.3), where it is published online⁶⁷. The piece was acquired in 1989 and is absent from de Haan (2019); its omission has been confirmed by direct comparison with the complete catalogue text and index. The Memphis shabti raises the documented total of known Hori I faience shabtis to at least 31. It documents a further, hitherto not systematically recorded dispersal line into academic collections in the USA.

These three main lines – archaeological core inventory, European art market, and American market – cannot be attributed to a single dispersal event. Rather, they indicate several temporally staggered processes of object removal and transfer.

The convergence of excavation inventory, museum holdings, and art market provenances supports a model of an early and successive dispersal phase. This began in all probability already in the early 20th century and led to the gradual dissolution of the original tomb inventory.

The most probable mechanism is undocumented removal of objects from the tomb context in the vicinity of Tell Basta, well documented for Nile Delta sites through agricultural activity and informal digging (sebakhin)⁶⁸. These processes explain in particular the early presence of comparable pieces in the art market prior to the official excavation.

⁶²Tell Basta. Cairo 1957.

<https://www.meretsgerbooks.com/pages/books/M0743b/habachi-labib/tell-basta>

⁶³de Haan, Niek: The shabtis of the King's Son of Kush Hori. 2019.

https://www.academia.edu/39314315/The_shabtis_of_the_Kings_Son_of_Kush_Hori

⁶⁴de Haan, Niek: The shabtis of the King's Son of Kush Hori. 2019.

https://www.academia.edu/39314315/The_shabtis_of_the_Kings_Son_of_Kush_Hori

⁶⁵Sotheby Parke-Bernet, New York, Sale 4324, 13 December 1979. Elizabeth and Marie Khayat, consignors. Lots 80-85. local:images/deep/Sothebys_1979_Sale4324_Lots80-85.pdf

⁶⁶Temple, Tomb and Dwelling. 1992.

<https://archive.org/details/templetombdwelli0000scot>

⁶⁷Missing source: MEMPHIS_HORI

⁶⁸Sebakhin note.

<https://www.ucl.ac.uk/museums-static/digitalegypt/archaeology/sebakhin.html>

The most recent archaeological reconstruction of the New Kingdom elite necropolis at Tell Basta by Auenmueller (2021) confirms this picture: the tombs of the viceroys Hori I and Hori II and of the vizier Iuty (tomb no. 1130) were located in close proximity in the mound north of the main temple — a cluster of high-ranking Ramesside officials used over several generations (late Dynasty XVIII to Dynasty XX)⁶⁹. The funerary equipment of the Iuty tomb appeared on the Cairo art market before 1926 (Auenmueller 2021, pp. 27–28), suggesting a parallel early dispersal pattern for the neighbouring Hori tombs as well.

Direct involvement by Habachi in the removal or transfer of finds is not demonstrable and cannot be derived from the present source material.

The present ushabti is therefore with high probability part of this pre-1944 dispersal phase and belongs to a more broadly distributed workshop series from the Tell Basta area.

⁶⁹Auenmüller, Johannes: The Ramesside Vizier Iuty from Bubastis. In: *Ägypten und Levante / Egypt and the Levant XXXI* (2021), pp. 15–43.

local:/Users/dirk/Uschabti_Collection_Beckers/Hori/Auenmueller-2021-Vizier-Iuty.pdf

Discussion

UB-014 is of research relevance precisely because it stands at the intersection of excavation context, object group, and art market history. Its scholarly value lies less in a fully secured find context than in the transparent reconstruction of the documentable and undocumented sections of its biography.

The preceding chapters demonstrate that the provenance of UB-014 can be established not through a seamless individual chain, but through the convergence of several independent indicators. These include the archaeological core inventory at Habachi ⁷⁰, the early typological comparability with the pieces published by Gauthier ⁷¹, the museum-based market line via Leiden/Moger ⁷², and the modernly documented American provenance via Elizabeth Khayat and the Harer collection ⁷³.

The so-called Khayat question is of central but methodologically limited significance: the embedding of Elizabeth Khayat in a family milieu demonstrably engaged with Egyptian antiquities increases the plausibility of the modern provenance, without a direct connection to Habachi or earlier excavators being demonstrable.

This twofold state of evidence is precisely what makes UB-014 of scholarly interest:

An additional finding arises from an inconsistency in Scott (1992): the present object clearly corresponds to catalogue entry no. 150 on p. 201 (including height and Sotheby's reference), while the illustration on p. 203 is incorrectly captioned as no. 151. The actual entry no. 151 (p. 202) describes an entirely different, larger ushabti (12.5 cm). This misattribution of the illustration explains the later confusion in de Haan (2019), who correctly identifies the object but adopts the incorrect number ⁷⁴. (see Fig. 9) (see Fig. 10) (see Fig. 11)

On the one hand, the modern provenance from 1979 is well documented; on the other hand, the discrepancy between the 15 ushabtis documented in 1944 and the currently known approximately 30 examples clearly indicates an earlier dispersal phase. The existence of multiple independent market lines – particularly the Dutch line (Leiden / Moger) and the American line (Khayat / Harer) – and the close typological correspondence of the pieces argue that the ushabtis of Hori I had entered circulation before the official excavation of 1944.

The convergence of these findings allows a consistent overall interpretation: the Hori I ushabtis are not isolated individual objects but fragments of a formerly coherent, serially produced tomb inventory, already partly detached from its original context in the early 20th century and fed into the international art market through various channels. In this model, the Khayat network functions not as the sole explanation but as a particularly well-traceable modern distribution line within a broader object history.

Against this background, UB-014 appears not as a singular object of unclear origin but as part of a historically traceable history of dispersal and collecting. The embedding in the Khayat network increases the plausibility of the modern provenance, but does not replace the necessary source-critical gradation between secured, plausible, and open sections of the object biography.

Finally, it should be noted that no evidence exists for Labib Habachi's own involvement in the removal or transfer of objects. The available data rather indicate a fragmentation of the find complex already underway before his excavation.

⁷⁰Tell Basta. Cairo 1957.

<https://www.meretsgerbooks.com/pages/books/M0743b/habachi-labib/tell-basta>

⁷¹Le tombeau de Hori. ASAE 28 (1928), pp. 133–138.

<images/deep/Gauthier-1928-133.pdf>

⁷²de Haan, Niek: The shabtis of the King's Son of Kush Hori. 2019.

https://www.academia.edu/39314315/The_shabtis_of_the_Kings_Son_of_Kush_Hori

⁷³Sotheby Parke-Bernet, New York, Sale 4324, 13 December 1979. Elizabeth and Marie Khayat, consignors. Lots 80-85.

local:images/deep/Sothebys_1979_Sale4324_Lots80-85.pdf

Temple, Tomb and Dwelling. 1992.

<https://archive.org/details/templetombdwelli0000scot>

⁷⁴Temple, Tomb and Dwelling. 1992.

<https://archive.org/details/templetombdwelli0000scot>

de Haan, Niek: The shabtis of the King's Son of Kush Hori. 2019.

https://www.academia.edu/39314315/The_shabtis_of_the_Kings_Son_of_Kush_Hori

In methodological terms, UB-014 underscores the importance of an interdisciplinary approach that links archaeological, typological, and provenance-historical data. Particularly in cases with fragmentary source material, a differentiated and source-critically graduated reconstruction of the object biography can thereby be achieved.

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147. SHAWABTI FIGURE OF A ROYAL SCRIBE

Painted wood
New Kingdom, Ramesside Period, Dynasty XIX-XX, ca. 1303-1085 B.C.
H. 27.8 cm. (11")

147. PROVENANCE:

Ex-collection Museum of Art and Archaeology, University of Missouri, Columbia.

147. BIBLIOGRAPHY:

Sotheby's (New York) 13 December 1979, lot no. 88.

148. SHAWABTI FIGURE

Terracotta
Second Intermediate Period, Dynasty XIV-XVII, ca. 1786-1558 B.C.
H. 13.3 cm. (5 1/4")

149. SHAWABTI FIGURE OF NAKHT

Painted terracotta
New Kingdom, Ramesside Period, Dynasty XIX-XX, ca. 1303-1085 B.C.
H. 6.3 cm. (2 1/2")

149. PROVENANCE:

Ex-collections Drexel, MIA (16.391).

149. PARALLELS:

Another example is in the Harer Family Trust collection, Ex-MIA 16.390, and it has been reported that two similar figures are in the collection of the Cleveland Museum of Art. See also Newberry (1957), pl. XXXIX, no. 47965.

150. SHAWABTI FIGURE OF THE VICEROY OF NUBIA, HORI I

White-glazed faience
New Kingdom, Dynasty XX, temp. Ramesses III, ca. 1192-1160 B.C.
H. 10.7 cm. (4 1/4")

150. PROVENANCE:

Bubastis, Tomb of Hori I.

150. BIBLIOGRAPHY:

Sotheby's (New York) 13 December 1979, lot no. 85.

150. LITERATURE:

Labib Habachi, *Tell Basta*, Cairo (1957), pp. 100-101, pl. XXXVIIb; Aubert (1974), p. 125, pl. 21, nos. 45-47.

Figure 1: Scott 1992, catalogue page p. 201

151

152 A-D

2
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3

Figure 2: Scott 1992, catalogue page p. 203

[80]

Another Property

■ 80 LIMESTONE STELE, Late Ptolemaic/early Roman Period, circa 1st Century B.C./1st Century A.D., carved in sunk relief with a king standing with his hands raised in praise before a figure of Horus, the king wearing a projecting kilt with bull's tail and uraei, broad collar, and girdle around the torso, his short hair surmounted by a plumed crown with solar disk and uraei, an offering table in the center, four columns of inscription including empty cartouches above. *11 x 10 inches (27.9 x 25.4 cm)*
See illustration

Property of Dr. Elizabeth Khayat

■ 81 ALABASTER USHABTI, 19th/20th Dynasty, 1305-1080 B.C., with protruding hands crossed over the chest and wearing a tripartite wig, the inscription, heft, pedestal and other details painted in traces of black, green, and red pigment. *Height 6 1/2 inches (16.5 cm)*

■ 82 WHITE FAIENCE USHABTI OF THE VICEROY HORI I, 20th Dynasty, 1196-1080 B.C., holding boxes, several implements suspended over the back, and wearing a broad collar and tripartite wig, the details and inscription painted in dark brown: "the Inspector, the Chis, the King's Son of Kush, the Royal Scribe Hory". *Height 4 1/4 inches (11.1 cm)*
Cf. Aubert, nos. 43-47; for Hori, royal Son of Kush under Ramesses III, see p. 125.
See illustration

■ 83 WHITE FAIENCE USHABTI OF THE VICEROY HORI I, 20th Dynasty, 1196-1080 B.C., similar to the preceding lot. *Height 4 1/4 inches (11.1 cm)*
See illustration

■ 84 WHITE FAIENCE USHABTI OF THE VICEROY HORI I, 20th Dynasty, 1196-1080 B.C., similar to the preceding. *Height 4 1/4 inches (11.1 cm)*
See illustration

■ 85 WHITE FAIENCE USHABTI OF THE VICEROY HORI I, 20th Dynasty, 1196-1080 B.C., similar to the preceding. *Height 4 1/4 inches (10.8 cm)*

[82]

[83]

[84]

Figure 3: Sotheby Parke-Bernet, New York, 13 December 1979, lot 85

[78] [167] [75] [71] [73] [168] [74]

[79] [76] [97] [80] [82]

Figure 6: Khayat 1924, general view of ushabtis

Figure 7: Detail no. 167

EGYPTIAN USHABTIU

or faience figurines which were buried to act as slaves and do the work of the dead in the coming world, such as ploughing the fields, watering the canals and carrying sand from east to west while the dead rested.

NUMBERS 166-175

166 FINE EGYPTIAN BLUE GLAZED USHABTI

12TH DYNASTY, 3000 B. C.

10 - Deep blue glaze with hieroglyphic inscription in black, from chapter 6 of The Book of the Dead. A remarkable state of preservation. Fine modeling. *Height, 6½ inches*

167 EGYPTIAN BLUE GLAZED USHABTI

18TH DYNASTY, 1500 B. C.

15 - Nearly similar to the preceding, but smaller. Very fine. *Height, 5½ inches*

[SEE ILLUSTRATION]

168 EGYPTIAN GREEN GLAZED USHABTI

18TH DYNASTY, 1500 B. C.

7½ - Beautiful light green glaze. Fine state of preservation. *Height, 5¼ inches*

[SEE ILLUSTRATION]

169 THREE EGYPTIAN USHABTIU 18TH DYNASTY, 1500 B. C.

12½ - Light blue glaze. Well preserved. (3) *Height, 4¼ inches*

170 TWO RARE EGYPTIAN USHABTIU

4TH DYNASTY, 4000 B. C.

12½ - Both represented as wearing garments; one blue glazed, the other of fine green glaze with decoration in black. (2)

Height, 4¼ inches

171 EGYPTIAN USHABTI

18TH DYNASTY, 1500 B. C.

10 - Light blue glaze, with hieroglyphic inscription from chapter 6 of The Book of the Dead. Well preserved. *Height, 6¼ inches*

172 TWO EGYPTIAN USHABTIU 18TH DYNASTY, 1500 B. C.

5 - Whitish color showing traces of the original blue glaze. *Height, 5 inches*

Figure 8: Catalogue description no. 167

151. SHAWABTI FIGURE OF THE PRIEST OF AMEN, HORI

Blue-glazed faience
New Kingdom, Dynasty XX, ca. 1200-1085 B.C.
H. 12.5 cm. (4 7/8")

151. CONDITION:

Broken and repaired with some restoration.

151. LITERATURE:

See Aubert (1974), pl. 40, figs. 95-96.

152. SHAWABTI FIGURES

Blue-glazed faience
Third Intermediate Period, Dynasty XXI, ca. 1085-945 B.C.

152 A. TAY-WEHERET

H. 10.5 cm. (4 1/8")

152 A. PROVENANCE:

Deir el-Bahari.

152 A. LITERATURE:

See Aubert (1974), pp. 141-143.

152 B. NES-TA-NEB-ISHERU

H. 15 cm. (6 7/8")

152 B. PROVENANCE:

Deir el-Bahari.

152 C. BAK-EN-MUT

H. 9.9 cm. (3 15/16")

152 C. PROVENANCE:

Deir el-Bahari, 1891 (Cache II).

152 C. PARALLELS:

Schneider (1974), no. 4.3.1.18.

152 D. QED-MERIT

H. 9.7 cm. (3 7/8")

152 D. PARALLELS

See Aubert (1974), pl. 51, fig. 120.

2
0
2

Figure 9: Scott 1992, p. 202, entry no. 151 (different object)

1 - 3

4 - 5

6

7

8

9 - 11

12

1-3 Aubert family collection

Published: Aubert, *Statuettes Egyptiennes Chaouabtis Ouchebtis* (Paris, 1974); fig 45 & 47 p. 292 pl. 21

Provenance: Unknown

Height: Between 10.8 and 11 centimeters

Comments: Nice examples with all different necklaces and clear Maat feather on the hoes.

4-5 Amasis collection

Published: No. © Amasis foundation.

Provenance: Ex D. van Dam, ex Moger, the Netherlands

Figure 10: de Haan 2019, p. 10, fig. 8

Height: Unknown

Comments: Intact examples.

6 Bouvier collection

Published: No. Exhibited Basel museum in 1999.

Provenance: Acquired by Maurice Bouvier prior to his move from Egypt to Switzerland in 1959

Height: 10.9 CM

Comments: Titles omitted.

7 De Haan collection

Published: No.

Provenance: Ex R. Ellis, New York, acquired in Egypt prior to 1966, sold by Hixenbaugh Ancient Art in 2013 to USA collector to current owner

Height: 11 CM

Comments: Intact.

8 Harer Family trust

Published: G. Scott, Temple, Tomb & Dwelling, Harer Family Trust Collection (Cal State Univ, 1992); pp. 202 - 203 no. 151

Provenance: Unknown

Height: 12.5 CM (according to the publication, doubtful considering the other objects)

Comments: Broken and repaired.

9-11: Sothebys, NYC, 13 Dec 1979

Published: Auction catalogue, lots 82 till 84

Provenance: Unknown

Height: Unknown

Comments: Middle and right example same as Sothebys 5-7-1982, Lots 164 -165.

12 Ede

Published: Charles Ede catalogue 1986, number 51.

Provenance: Unknown

Height: Unknown

Comments: Ib amulet on the chest?

Figure 11: de Haan 2019, p. 11